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All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture

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Report

Contents

1	Summary.....	6
2	Introduction.....	6
3	Methodology	7
4	Aquaculture EU Legal Framework.....	9
4.1	IMTA EU Legal Framework	12
5	Aquaculture National Legal Framework.....	12
5.1	IMTA's status within the national legislative framework.....	19
6	ASTRAL IMTA sites: Local, Regional, National level analysis	20
6.1	Argentina	21
6.1.1	National	21
6.1.2	Regional.....	24
6.1.3	Local.....	25
6.2	Brazil.....	27
6.2.1	National	27
6.2.2	Regional.....	30
6.3	Ireland.....	30
6.3.1	National	30
6.3.2	Local.....	35
6.4	Scotland.....	35
6.4.1	National	35
6.5	South Africa	40
6.5.1	National	40
6.5.2	Regional.....	45
6.5.3	Local.....	45
7	Recommendations.....	46

8	Further considerations	47
9	References.....	49

List of Tables

Table 1: Legislative and regulatory framework relevant to low-trophic aquaculture in Scottish inshore waters, arranged alphabetically	12
Table 2: Aquaculture National Legal Framework	14
Table 3: Other Aquaculture Regulations	19
Table 4: Typology of government's acceptance of IMTA. Promotional: accelerate the development of IMTA; permissive: neutral toward IMTA; precautionary: slow the development of IMTA; preventative: block or ban the uptake of IMTA.	20

List of Figures

<i>Figure 1</i> ASTRAL's IMTA sites	21
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ACRONYMS:

CAP: Common Agricultural Policy

CAR: Controlled Activities Regulations

CE: Circular Economy

CFP: Common Fisheries Policy

CMO: Common Organisation of Agricultural Markets

DFFE: Department of Forestry, Fisheries, and the Environment.

EIA: Environmental Impact Assessment

EU: European Union

HMPA: Highly Protected Areas

IMTA: Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture

IUCN: International Union for Conservation

MPA: Marine Protected Areas

POs: Producer Organisations

WFD: Water Framework Directive

1 Summary

This report aims at carrying out a review of aquaculture legislation to provide a current overview of the regulatory framework, first focusing on Europe and then covering the national, regional, and local levels. This revision allows to identify the status of aquaculture innovations such as IMTA systems in the current legislative frameworks of Europe and several Atlantic countries. To do so, in addition to the extensive literature review and workshops, several semi-structured interviews were conducted with different stakeholders such as producers, academics, scientists, policymakers, and experts covering a wide array of diverse actors on the subject to have a better and broader understanding of the aquaculture practices within the contexts that constitute ASTAL's project.

To have diverse perspectives on the matter is crucial for this task's purpose since it aims to represent all possible angles of this complex regulatory affairs, going beyond an academic or legal dimension.

Moreover, this document also aims to provide information regarding successful aquaculture or IMTA practices worldwide, emphasizing IMTA to ultimately contribute to the policy recommendations dialogue to enhance its development.

2 Introduction

It is no secret that there have been various and serious efforts to regulate aquaculture practices around the world. This can be observed through the extensive regulatory documentation issued by several countries at different administrative levels, such as national laws, acts, conduct codes, codes of best practices and practice guidelines, among others. These can cover a wide range of related topics, from general concerns to more specific actions. Nevertheless, each regulation is indispensable for building a broader understanding of aquaculture matters.

Aquaculture represents the biggest sector of food production nowadays. Nevertheless, one of its main limitations is the environmental impact it generates. In this sense, IMTA systems were introduced to address this issue. These practices integrate the cultivation of species from different trophic levels. "Uneaten feed, solid wastes and dissolved nutrients are turned into healthy food, making IMTA a driver for ecologically sustainable aquaculture. Sustainable coastal and marine aquaculture development requires a holistic approach that involves social/cultural, economic, as well as environmental sustainability" (Hossain, Senff & Glaser, 2022).

One of the main concerns to successfully develop IMTA systems is the current legislative framework which in many cases constitutes a barrier to fully developing IMTA systems, being in-shore or offshore, smaller, or bigger productions, for local or international consumption. The aim of this document is to give some insights and afterwards some recommendations on the actual barriers and possible enablers at the different levels of government policies and regulations. As mentioned before, those

recommendations are founded on literature review (including primary and grey literature). Importantly, they strongly lay on the real concerns on the fields from diverse actors related to the aquaculture system and IMTA in the Atlantic, emphasizing countries involved in the ASTRAL project: Argentina, Brazil, Ireland, Scotland, and South Africa. Finally, we highlight some interesting practices worldwide which also nourishes the remarks and recommendations from this work.

The final objective of the recommendations identified is to be used at different specified levels, ranging from local to national in those countries, and considering the European and Atlantic levels to unleash IMTA systems.

3 Methodology

Desktop and empirical studies on governance, policy, food safety/consumer trust, and social acceptability were conducted. Existing regulatory frameworks, policies and legislation review related to aquaculture systems in the EU, Argentina, Brazil, Ireland, Scotland, South Africa, and other countries was developed in order to comprehend the situation at different administrative levels and to detect opportunities and challenges when introducing more sustainable and innovative aquaculture practices.

A total of 35 semi-structured interviews were carried out including the contribution of key actors in the aquaculture industry within their respective countries. Producers, researchers, scientists, and experts were able to provide their valuable input. Additionally, in this document we include the insights from 4 workshops conducted in the 5 countries of the ASTRAL IMTA sites (in the frame of T7.6, summarized in D7.6 -Public Perception and Awareness) where policies and consumers issues were discussed. Furthermore, a policy recommendation workshop took place on November 8th, 2023, in Barcelona with the participation of expert researchers. This shared fundamental information regarding aquaculture practices and its innovative technologies in Canada, Spain and in the UK. The development of this workshop was very beneficial as IMTA experiences that are being developed around the world were shared. In addition, themes such as food safety, participatory approaches in decision-making procedures and social acceptability were addressed, as well as an overview of the legislation at the European and national levels.

Lastly, a review of several projects at European level integrating policy recommendations regarding aquaculture practices was completed. Projects such as AQUAVITAE, GAIN, IMPAQT, IFISHIENCI, INTEGRATE and others were taken into consideration.

After data collection was completed, a codification structure was developed to organize and analyse all the information gathered through the literature review (primary articles, grey literature, and European projects), workshops and semi-structured interviews. Four main themes were taken into consideration: 1) Policy domain, 2) Environmental dimension, 3) Social dimension, 4) Communication domain. Moreover, within these four topics, other main features were included in, such as: certification schemes, customs policies, administrative bureaucracy, dissemination strategies, circularity aspects, and environmental aspects. The coding structure was applied to every country within the ASTRAL project.

A concept or approach was developed to construct every dimension which are described in the following manner:

Policy dimension: to constitute this domain, several elements were taken into account. For example, the administrative procedures to obtain a licence, the role of the regulatory agencies, political will of government institutions to promote aquaculture and IMTA practices, schemes or strategies being established to ensure its development. Furthermore, grants and subsidies were also included within this domain as well as participatory approach and encouragement of stakeholders' active involvement.

Environmental dimension: This dimension is based on features such as the adoption of plans to mitigate the effects of climate change, the efforts of protect the environment during the implementation of aquaculture practices and the establishment of monitoring systems that verify if industry is complying with environmental legislation. Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) were also discussed. Furthermore, the perspective of stakeholders regarding this dimension was extremely valuable as they understand the importance of performing activities in a manner that results in low environmental impact. Finally, it is valuable to underline that the environmental dimension is strongly linked to legislative matters.

Social dimension: consumer acceptance, marketability, efforts to enhance trust in aquaculture practices, the relevance and influence of local groups of interest, food safety, and the social culture of a certain context were elements considered for the structure of this dimension. Employment opportunities and the relationship between industry and local communities were also covered. In this regard, population's acceptance has a major impact on the feasibility of carrying out an aquaculture operation. In some context, these have been blocked by community resistance.

Communication dimension: communication is key within aquaculture advancement. Therefore, in this domain the implementation of active communication channels involving actors from several spheres such as academics, regulators, industry, and producers was considered. The development of projects integrating industry with various partnerships from the beginning were also taken into account as they are more likely to have a bigger impact. In addition, the willingness of communicating research outcomes among private companies including technological centres and other research institutions was also incorporated. Lastly, it is worth highlighting that knowledge exchange must not only be shared among scientific or academic audiences, but it should also involve producers, industry operators and government agents, hence, it was also addressed within this dimension.

On the other hand, and as previously highlighted, it's not the intention of this task to repeat information presented in drafts by other similar projects, but to build on their knowledge and go deeper for specific recommendations which are not only considering the global perspective but the local one as well. Therefore, a different approach was undertaken to focus on local knowledge and try to combine bottom-up and top-down approaches to summarize policy recommendations which consider (and learn from) specificities and contexts.

4 Aquaculture EU Legal Framework

The Water Framework Directive (WFD) has been the main law for water protection in Europe since 2000. It contemplates the inland, transitional, and coastal surface waters as well as groundwaters and aims at ensuring an *"integrated approach to water management, respecting the integrity of whole ecosystems, including by regulating individual pollutants and setting corresponding regulatory standards."* It is also supported by two other directives that involve *"quality and quantity of groundwater and the quality of surface water"*. (European Commission, n.d).

Following the development of this primary regulation, in June 2008 the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive 2008/56/EC was adopted as a form to protect the marine environment across Europe. In this regard, this Directive indicates that Member States must develop marine strategies aimed at achieving or maintaining "good environmental status", which is defined as *"different uses made of the marine resources are conducted at a sustainable level, ensuring their continuity for future generations"*. Moreover, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive is conceived within a holistic framework. In this regard, is based on existing EU legislation, such as the WFD.

Also, in 2009 the EC Regulation No 1224/2009 was enacted focusing on control and monitoring matters. The adequate implementation of control measurements by each Member State of aquaculture products within the supply chain helps to ensure the sustainability and profitability of EU

aquaculture. Furthermore, it aims at ensuring compliance with the rules of the common fisheries policy. On the other hand, traceability obligations permit us to identify the origin of the products (including products imported from non-EU countries) and is a practical form to prevent fraud.

Another relevant factor within aquaculture legal framework is that fish farmers can be recognized as producer organisations (PO's) throughout the CMO Regulation (EU) N° 1379/2013. Nevertheless, aquaculture producers have expressed the complexity of the setting up a PO, especially for small-scale producers. In addition, they have been experiencing difficulties to be recognized as POs under this regulation. This might be caused by financial means and administrative hurdles.

On the other hand, The Common Fisheries Policy Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013) aims at ensuring in the long-term that fishing and aquaculture practices are environmentally sustainable, while also aligning with the objectives of accomplishing economic, social and employment benefits. It also englobes aspects regarding the combat against IUU finishing activities. The introduction of this regulation is quite relevant since it incorporates essential aspects related to IMTA practices such as social and employment dimensions.

The Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (Directive 2014/89/EU) sets up the framework for Marine Spatial Planning, which seeks to promote *“the sustainable growth of maritime economies, the sustainable development of marine areas and the sustainable use of marine resources”*. In the Integrated Maritime Policy of the European Union, this basis lays out the application by Member States of maritime spatial planning with the purpose of contributing to the established goals of *“sustainable development of energy sectors at sea, of maritime transport, and of the fisheries and aquaculture sectors, and to the preservation, protection and improvement of environment, including resilience to climate change impacts”*. It is important to emphasize that this doesn't interfere with legislation dictated by Member States regarding territorial land.

The legislation 2017/62 establishes a set out rules for EU official controls to ensure the proper application of legislation regarding agri-food chains to protect human health, animal health and welfare, and plant health. It also, addresses the control monitoring of live bivalve molluscs from their harvesting waters.

Furthermore, the Commission proposal for a new Fisheries Control Regulation COM/2018/368 covers matters related to traceability in regard to all aquaculture products, extended also to products imported from non-EU countries.

On the other hand, the new regulation (EU) 2019/6 (veterinary medicinal) helps increase the availability of veterinary medicines for aquaculture, meaning that, *“sufficient and effective veterinary*

medicinal products should be available in the Union in order to ensure high standards of public and animal health, and for the development of the agriculture and aquaculture sectors.”

These regulatory documents represent a value path towards the regulation of aquaculture practices. More in-depth measures have been developed through the European Green Deal. Among its diverse goals, this deal aims at contributing to achieving a circular economy considering actions such as *“combating food fraud, including strengthening enforcement and investigate capacity at EU level, and to launch a process to identify new innovative food and feed products, such as seafood based on algae”*. In addition, aspects regarding consumers behaviour are introduced, meaning that, *“The Commission will explore new ways to give consumers better information, including by digital means, on details such as where the food comes from, its nutritional value, and its environmental footprint”*. Furthermore, the creation of new jobs is addressed within this deal. It is stated that *“the circular economy offers great potential for new activities and jobs”*.

More specifically, the Farm to Fork Strategy includes innovative aspects within the aquaculture sector. It lays out the potential of this practice to mitigate climate change through, for example, carbon-sequestration (through cultivation of seaweed and molluscs). Furthermore, it aims at achieving at least 25% of EU’s agricultural land under organic farming by 2030, but it also sets the goal of increasing organic aquaculture.

The Action Plan for the development of organic production also addresses measures to foster organic farming within the EU (COM (2021) 141 final). Under this premise and concerning the aquaculture activity, the new Strategic Guidelines for sustainable development of EU aquaculture aims at promoting organic aquaculture. In addition, *“the Commission encourages EU Member States to include the increase of organic aquaculture among the objectives of their reviewed Multi-annual National Strategic Plans for aquaculture. Furthermore, the Commission staff working document on a sea basin perspective to guide the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF) programming stipulates that the EMFF (future European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund, EMFAF) should be used to promote sustainable aquaculture practices such as organic production”*. Furthermore, this plan also addresses interesting matter such local supply chains and exchanges of best practices between public canteens and restaurants, as well as the availability of organic products in canteens in order to reach a broader target. Lastly, it states that *“a sustainable and resilient agricultural and aquaculture sector depends on enhanced biodiversity, which is fundamental for a healthy ecosystem and critical for maintaining nutrients cycles in the soil, clean water, and pollinators. Increased biodiversity allows farmers to adapt better to climate change.”*

On the other hand, the document adopted in 2021 *“Strategic guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture for the period 2021 to 2030 (COM (2021) 236 final)”* sets a series of

recommendations that emerged from close consultation with different bodies, administrations, and stakeholders such as, EU Member States, Aquaculture Advisory Council, public consultation, as well as the opinions of the European Parliament on the development of EU aquaculture.

Moreover, this document refers to the current efforts to develop a specific initiative to encourage the *“production, safe consumption and innovative use of algae”*. According to the Farm to Fork strategy, algae *“should become an important source of alternative protein for sustainable food system and global food security.”*

4.1 IMTA EU Legal Framework

One of the primary regulations concerning these systems is Regulation No. 767/2009, especially Article 6^o. In this regard, IMTA practices are potentially limited since it removes the *“option of introducing filter-feeders or detritivores in the facility which feed directly on fish waste”* This also represents a setback in the contribution of IMTA systems to the implementation of CE in aquaculture practices within the EU.

5 Aquaculture National Legal Framework

Several countries have developed aquaculture regulations to address practices within their territory. For instance, Scotland has elaborated an extensive legal framework addressing these practices, such as low-trophic systems. In this regard, the following table lists regulations regarding aquaculture practices, especially low-trophic aquaculture (Table 1).

Table 1: Legislative and regulatory framework relevant to low-trophic aquaculture in Scottish inshore waters, arranged alphabetically

Law	Relevance
Aquaculture and Fisheries (Scotland) Act 2013	Regulation of finfish farms and designation of Shellfish Water Protected Areas (SWPA, where wild as well as farmed shellfish is grown)
Aquatic Animal Health (Scotland) Regulations 2009 (amended 2011) (Replaces the Registration of Fish Farming and Shellfish Farming Businesses Order 1985-as amended)	Requires the authorisation of all Aquaculture Production Businesses (APB's) by MS-FHI; implements European Directive 2006/88/EC on animal health requirements for aquaculture animals and products thereof, and on the prevention and control of certain diseases in aquatic animals.
[UK] Conservation (Natural Habitats etc) Regulations as amended: the 'Habitats Regulations'	Farms may require a Habitats Regulations Assessment (HRA) if siting in Marine Protected Area (MPA)

Environmental Assessment (Scotland) Act 2005	Requires Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) of significant public plans and policies
Environmental Impact Assessment (Scotland) Regulations 1999; The Town and Country Planning (Marine Fish Farming) (Scotland) Order 2007; The Town and Country Planning (Environmental Assessment) (Scotland) Regulations 2017; and others: in total the 'EIA regulations'	Require EIA (for scrutiny by public bodies and public); The 2007 order restricted the requirement to finfish farms (i.e., shellfish and seaweed farming are currently exempt).
Food (Scotland) Act 2015	Established Foods Standards Scotland (FSS)
Marine (Scotland) Act 2010	Gave The Scottish Government (SG) (and, operationally, Marine Science (MS)) powers over marine planning, marine licensing, and nature conservation. Requires SG to prepare and adopt a single National Marine Plan, covering inshore and offshore waters, sets the context of Marine Regions and Regional Marine Plans. Requires all farms to have a Marine License in respect of navigation.
Regulation (EU) 2017/625	Regulates all aspects of the agri-food chain, including marine organisms and organic products
Scottish Crown Estate Act 2019	Provides a framework for Crown Estate Scotland to develop management of its assets (including leasing of seabed), with provisions for further devolution of management to local authorities, island councils, public bodies, and community organisations, within a national governance framework.
Scottish Marine Regions Order 2015	Delineates 11 Marine Regions
Marine Strategy Regulations 2010 (and Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848)	Transferred Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) (2008/56/EC) into UK legislation. Defines assessment of marine waters, good environmental status (GES), targets and indicators, monitoring, and measures; with 2017 decision setting criteria and methodological standards on GES of marine waters and standardisation of monitoring and assessment methods.
[UK] Marine and Coastal Access Act 2009	Provides executive devolution to Scottish Ministers of the marine planning and conservation powers in the offshore region (12-200 nm), in line with previous executive devolution of marine licensing. Includes marine policy statement (MPS), marine planning, marine licensing, marine conservation, and common enforcement powers
Marine Licensing (Exempted Activities) (Scottish inshore regions) Order 2011	Regulates exemptions from need for marine licence, including for deposit and removal of equipment whilst fish farming (including crustaceans and molluscs)
[UK] The Marine Environment (Amendment) (EU Exit) Regulations 2018	Provides amendments to the Marine Coastal Access Act 2009, Marine Strategy Regulations 2010, Marine Licensing order 2011,

	given the withdrawal of the UK from the EU, and provisions in consideration of the devolution settlement.
Scotland Act 1998	Extend responsibilities of the Scottish Parliament to legislate activities relevant to the marine environment in inshore waters, with some matters reserved (i.e. oil, gas).
Town & Country Planning (Scotland) Act 1997 as amended by the Town and Country Planning (Marine Fish Farming). (Scotland) Act 2007 and in subsequent regulations	Provides the basis for the terrestrial planning system and sets out the roles of the Scottish Ministers and local authorities with regard to development plans, development management and enforcement; fin-fish farms within inshore waters currently require planning permission from local authority; other types of farms only require such permission for shore-based structures
Water Environment and Water Services (Scotland) Act 2003; Water Environment	WEWSSA 2003 implemented Water Framework Directive (WFD) in Scotland and made finfish farm developments subject to Local Authority
(Controlled Activities) (Scotland) Regulations 2005 and updates	Planning control: the 2005 regulations oblige environment-impacting activities to apply for a Controlled Activities Regulations (CAR) licence
Water Environment (Shellfish Water Protected Areas: Environmental Objectives etc.) (Scotland) Regulations 2013	Deals with environmental objectives and Programmes of Measures for Shellfish Water Protected Areas (SWPA).

Source: Aquavivae project (2021). Deliverable D8.1. Report on current policy frameworks for aquaculture.

Furthermore, after conducting a literature review it was found that the following countries have made efforts to regulate aquaculture practices at national level. Nonetheless, each country features different regulations for this practice. In France, aquaculture is not regulated as a whole, inland fisheries legislation applies to inland aquaculture (*pisciculture continentale*), whereas mariculture (*élevages marins, cultures marines*) is regulated under marine fisheries legislation.

Table 2: Aquaculture National Legal Framework

Countries	National regulations
Argentina	National Aquaculture Law (2015). Many provinces have adhered to this law, for example: Tierra del Fuego.
Canada	The Canadian Shellfish Sanitation Program prevented shellfish and finfish from being raised within 125 m of each other. This was amended to accommodate IMTA.
Cyprus	The Cyprus National Strategic Plan 2007–2013 for Fisheries (Department of Fisheries and Marine

	<p>Research (DFMR), undated) is the current policy framework under which aquaculture lies.</p> <p>National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture 2014–202</p>
<p>France</p>	<p>Decree No.53-578 establishing the categories of classified installations.</p> <p>Decree No.77-1133 implementing Law No.76-663 concerning classified installations for the protection of environment.</p> <p>Decree No.77-1141 implementing article 2 of Law No.76-269 concerning the protection of nature.</p> <p>Rural code: Order of April 10th, 1997, establishing the health policy applicable to the marketing of aquaculture animals and products.</p> <p>Order of July 19th, 2002, establishing the health conditions for the import and transit, in the metropolitan territory and in the overseas departments, of live animals and some of their products as defined in article L 236- 1 of the Rural Code.</p> <p>Public Health Code.</p> <p>Draft Law on Water.</p> <p>Decree January 9th, 1852, on Maritime Fisheries</p> <p>Decree of August 20th, 1939, concerning the salubrity of oysters, mussels and other shellfish</p> <p>Decree No.85-453 implementing Law No.83-630 concerning the democratization of public enquiries and the protection of the environment.</p> <p>Decree No.85-453 implementing Law No.83-630 concerning the democratization of public enquiries and the protection of the environment.</p>

	<p>Decree No.91-1283 concerning the quality objectives of watercourses, parts of watercourses, canals, lakes or ponds and marine waters within the territorial zone.</p> <p>Decree No.2002-897 concerning the functions of the Ministry of Agriculture, Food, Fisheries and Rural Affairs.</p> <p>Decree No.2004-320 concerning the functions of the Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport, Land Use, Tourism, and the Sea.</p> <p>Law No.42-427 concerning maritime navigation titles.</p> <p>Law No.91-411 concerning the interprofessional organization of marine fisheries and aquaculture, and the organization of shellfish culture.</p> <p>Decree No.91-1276 regulating the functioning of interprofessional shellfish culture organizations.</p> <p>Decree No.92-335 regulating the functioning of the National Committee for Maritime Fisheries and Marine Aquaculture, as well as the Regional and Local Committees for Maritime Fisheries and Marine Aquaculture.</p> <p>Law No.97-1051 on Maritime Fisheries and Mariculture Law No.97-1051 on Maritime Fisheries and mariculture.</p> <p>Decree No.83-228 establishing the authorization system for marine aquaculture.</p>
Italy	<p>The national fisheries and aquaculture policy currently consists of a 3-year plan, the “National Triennial Programme for Fisheries and Aquaculture 2013-2015”. Several strategic objectives have been set in this plan including improving the image of the sector, strategic diversification of aquaculture activities, administrative simplification particularly for licensing and site selection for aquaculture.</p>
	<p>“A sustainable aquaculture</p>

<p style="text-align: center;">Norway</p>	<p>industry is an industry that is competitive, market-oriented, and environmentally and resource-friendly, and that supplies safe seafood of good quality.” (Norwegian Ministry of Fisheries and Ocean Affairs, 2008)</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>The Aquaculture Act (2005) (the Act)</u></p> <p>to promote the profitability and competitiveness of the aquaculture industry within the framework of a sustainable development and contribute to the creation of value on the coast." The Act regulates both commercial aquaculture, as well as aquaculture carried out for scientific or educational purposes. The Act establishes a licensing system, and broadly applies to issues like environmental standards, land utilisation, registration, transfer, and mortgaging of licences, as well as control and enforcement.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Portugal</p>	<p>Regulatory Decree No. 9/2008, of 18 March - Defines the fundamental rules for the establishment of aquaculture production areas (APA) in the open sea (offshore)</p> <p>Decree-Law No. 152/2009, of 2 June - Transposes Directive 2006/88/EC, of the Council, of 24 October, on animal health requirements applicable to aquaculture animals and derived products, into the internal legal order.</p> <p>Decree-Law No. 40/2017, of 4 April, approves the legal regime for the installation and exploitation of culture establishments in marine waters, including transition waters, and in inland waters, using the legislative authorization granted. by Law No. 37/2016, of 15 December. This Decree-Law applies to establishments of cultures in marine waters and inland waters and, also, to related establishments, located in private property, private domain of the State, public domain of the State and of the local authorities, including the public domain water. The provisions of this Decree-Law are not applicable to State aquaculture posts, aquaculture units or captive aquaculture species with</p>

	<p>exclusive self-consumption, ornamental, didactic, technical, or scientific purposes.</p> <p>Ordinance No. 276/2017, of 18 September, establishes the regime and the amount of the deposit intended to guarantee, at the time of the termination of the Aquaculture Activity Title (TAA), the good environmental status of the marine environment and water bodies marine and inland waters, as well as the removal of works and mobile structures inserted in the area or volume assigned to the title.</p> <p>Ordinance No. 279/2017, of 19 September, sets out the instructional elements that must be submitted by the interested party in the procedures provided for in paragraph 2 of article 8, paragraph 2 of article 9, paragraph 1 of article 12 and in no. 2 of article 13 of Decree-Law No. 40/2017, of 4 April, which defines the legal regime for the installation and operation of cultural establishments in marine waters, including transition waters, and inland waters.</p> <p>Ordinance No. 280/2017, of 19 September, establishes the method of calculation, the amount, exemptions, the form of division and delivery of the collection product for the Aquaculture Fee (TAQ).</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">South Africa</p>	<p>Right to engage in aquaculture is required by the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and Environment (DFFE) when undertaking any commercial marine aquaculture activity, in terms of section 18 of marine living resources.”</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Act, 1998 (Act Nº 18 of 1998) (MLRA)</p>

In addition to all the legal framework presented above, some countries have established other types of regulations such as codes of conducts, codes of best practices, practice guidelines that usually address issues as quality standards (Table 3).

Table 3: Other Aquaculture Regulations

Country	Code of conduct	Codes of best practices	Practice guidelines
Canada	Code of conduct for responsible aquaculture: This code is based on the hazard analysis and critical control point (HACCP) system indicating standards for fish health, environmental quality, and product traceability.		
United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland		Quality Assurance scheme: in which members must meet standards of quality and environmental management that are internationally recognized such as ISO 14001. Codes of best practice that cover disease control, welfare, health and safety, and separate environmental codes are also envisaged (Howarth, 2006).	
Thailand	Code of conduct: Demands international quality standards. This code incorporates standards for deed, drugs use and environmental protection.		Good Aquaculture Practice guidelines: Responsible husbandry of shrimp.

5.1 IMTA's status within the national legislative framework

There are not any policies or regulations that specifically address the development of IMTA practices. Nevertheless, there are regulatory frameworks that seek to encourage more sustainable aquaculture. For instance, in Galicia (Spain) the Galician Aquaculture Strategy (ESGA) has been established to design and manage the aquaculture activity in the territory. In this regard, the strategy aims at promoting the development of employment opportunities and wealth in a balanced manner, with environmental respect and integration through the reconfiguration of aquaculture. However, it is also stated that IMTA still requires a current legal framework to address aspects such as, legal security, economic feasibility, and environmental sustainability.

Furthermore, this situation can be observed in other regions as well. For instance, in South Africa this practice can be carried out under integrated permits, whereas in Portugal it can be implemented under

polyculture licence. Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that *“the absence of regulatory or economic benefits from offsetting nutrient discharges and of approaches which value ecosystem services is challenging for business models. Legal and regulatory uncertainty on biosecurity and food safety is problematic”*. (Aquavivae, 2023).

There might be regulations that either promote or hinder the expansion of aquaculture and IMTA practices specifically. In this regard, Alexander et al., (2015) present a framework that *“characterizes the inter-relationship between the policy and regulations governing IMTA development”* (Table 4).

Table 4: Typology of government’s acceptance of IMTA. Promotional: accelerate the development of IMTA; permissive: neutral toward IMTA; precautionary: slow the development of IMTA; preventative: block or ban the uptake of IMTA.

	Promotional	Permissive	Precautionary	Preventive
<i>High-level aquaculture policies/regulations</i>				
National aquaculture policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Strategic Policy which aims to develop aquaculture e.g. innovation and technology, diversification of activities, improved marketing 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of dedicated aquaculture policy 	
Aquaculture relevant agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‘One-stop-shop’ 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Myriad agencies dealing with different aspects of aquaculture 	
<i>Control of planning</i>				
Authorisation/Licensing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> License for installation and operation of farm issued by one agency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Several other licenses may be required e.g. a town planning permit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Authorisation required at national, regional and local levels Lack of licensing arrangements for IMTA species e.g. algae 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disallowing two distinct species to be grown together
Access to land and water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dedicated spatial planning for aquaculture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General land planning regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU Directives (Wild Birds, Habitats, Water etc.) prevent development in areas of high natural value. 	
Environmental impact assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental impact assessment required – if IMTA mediating factor in environmental impact 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of comprehensive framework for aquaculture EIA 	
<i>Control of operations</i>				
Water and wastewater	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discharge licenses – if IMTA improves levels 			
Fish movement and disease control			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offence to spread disease 	
Drugs and pesticides		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strictly controlled through multitude of EU regulations 		
Feed		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strictly controlled through multitude of EU regulations 		
Food safety		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aquaculture specific food-safety legislation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No legislation re food safety of IMTA products leading to market-based problems 	

Source: Alexander, K. A., Potts, T. P., Freeman, S., Israel, D., Johansen, J., Kletou, D., ... & Angel, D. L. (2015). *The implications of aquaculture policy and regulation for the development of integrated multi-trophic aquaculture in Europe*

6 ASTRAL IMTA sites: Local, Regional, National level analysis

As explained above, 35 semi-structure interviews were carried out in Argentina, Brazil, Ireland, Scotland, and South Africa covering several topics regarding aquaculture and IMTA systems. These not only provide crucial information about the legislative framework of each country, but also address key issues such as, social licence to operate (SLO), certification and licensing procedures and communication approaches that strongly influence the development of aquaculture practices.

Figure 1 ASTRAL's IMTA sites

6.1 Argentina

6.1.1 National

6.1.1.1 Policy dimension

In Argentina, the National Aquaculture Department operates as a leading actor in the legislative sphere in the country. At the regional level there is no key actor since different entities intervene. Moreover, in 2015 the Aquaculture National Law was enacted. Not all the chapters are delimited, meaning that this law is not yet completely regulated. Hence, its evolution is quite gradual. Some provinces (including Tierra del Fuego) have adhered to this national law, but later a new law was introduced that prohibited aquaculture activities in the province (with some exceptions). In this regard, the legislation is ambiguous, and rules are not clear for the agents involved in these practices.

Furthermore, within the legislation there are still some legal loops that might hinder the development of certain practices within the aquaculture industry. For example, Law N° 244 indicates that the introduction of algae depends on the application authority. This is quite ambiguous since this depends on one designated person and there are not regular frameworks or any sort of guidelines that dictate whether the introduction of algae is possible, let alone the procedure to do so.

Legislation should enable the establishment of continuous and rigorous monitoring systems to ensure the adequate and desirable development of the aquaculture industry. Both the legislative framework

and the government's capacity for control are fundamental since both are interrelated; without control mechanisms, the legislative framework will not be effective. In other words, the obligations dictated by the law will not be complied. It's not enough to issue a fine, but some other penalties need to be applied to ensure that the operations produce the lowest environmental impact.

Under this premise, an economic reward system can be introduced to recognize sustainable practices through financial incentives, for example, by implementing circularity features during production. Furthermore, mechanism like carbon credits, blue credits, and nutrient trading taxes can also be pursued. Nevertheless, stakeholders are unaware of the status of these mechanisms in the country. Hence, it would be beneficial to explore this subject and receive information and guidance on how to acquire them.

Regarding licencing procedures, it is essential to emphasize that in Argentina, in general, administrative management is quite slow and not fluid. Furthermore, each province determines its own process. Hence, experiences when dealing with this procedure are different and not easy to share. But the idea behind that is not a simple process that involves a lot of paperwork, and several steps are shared among producers. Despite its complex procedure, the openness to producers is valued. Strategies such as the creation of a platform in which industry can shared their experiences and provide support to other producers as well as streamlining could facilitate the procedure.

Lastly, it is stated that the regulatory framework of other countries, such as Chile could serve as a structure or guide to develop its own legislation, adapting it to the Argentinean context.

6.1.1.2 Environmental dimension

In the national context, there is no regulations addressing the incorporation of IMTA systems within the aquaculture framework. In addition, it is mentioned by several stakeholders that circularity aspects should be included within the legislation. These can be addressed throughout economic incentives such as subsidies or tax/royalty incentive to promote novel techniques within the aquaculture production, such as IMTA. In addition, the importance of creating a balance between economic development and environmental matters has been reiterated by industry.

6.1.1.3 Social dimension

Certifications and social acceptance are strongly linked to each other. The more certifications and labels that enhance the quality of the product are used, the easier it is to be positively perceived by

society. For instance, currently there are different types of labels available that add value to a certain product, such as: ecolabels or regarding responsible fishing. Others are required by customs authorities as part of a clearance process, such as the certificate of origin. Product traceability is critical and there is also a social and ethical component within the traceability of the product, for example if the product comes from illegal fishing or the labour conditions within the vessels.

In addition, it is relevant to consider exportation destinations. Producers are more likely to be interested in using certifications when trying to reach a certain market, such as the American or European ones. The type of certification used depends on the destination a producer intends to reach. There are certifications or requirements at local, regional, national, or international level. However, investment is needed in the certification procedure.

Under this premise, certifications are perceived by interviewees as a mere instrument to expand products to new markets. Although certification schemes are key for the adequate development of aquaculture production, local context reality needs to be taken into consideration. The reality of the Argentinean context focuses on improving its social economy.

6.1.1.4 Communication dimension

Currently, in Argentina, at national level there has been an important political change opening a new array of possibilities since the institution of the aquaculture directorate has been created in 2020. This recently established agency is led by a director who believes in aquaculture and is actively pursuing to improve it. For instance, CATA commission (Comisión Asesora Técnica para la Acuicultura) was created under this person's management. CATA is composed of representatives of the Ministry of Agriculture, Farming and Fishing, Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development; National Institute of Agricultural Technology (INTA), the National Service of Agrifood Health and Quality (SENASA); National Institute of Fishing Research and Development (INIDEP); and National Institute of Industrial Technology (INTI).

The Commission analyses and evaluates aquaculture projects for financing through the National Fund for Aquaculture Development (FONAC) stipulated in the National Aquaculture Law No. 27,231. CATA's activities are coordinated by the Undersecretariat of Fisheries and Aquaculture of the Ministry of Agriculture, Farming and Fisheries, through its National Directorate of Aquaculture.

The existence of this type of organization represents undoubtedly a positive step towards aquaculture development. However, the dissemination strategy needs to be reinforced. Producers have stated that they are unaware of the opportunities offered by this agency, such as, the possibility of submitting a project for financing. One of the main issues regarding communication is that the website is very unintuitive, and that information has to be actively browsed until it is found. Also, there is no system for sending newsletters with news relevant to the stakeholders involved in the aquaculture industry. This could be a feature that could be included in the communication strategy for the agency, as well as intensifying its visibility in social media.

6.1.2 Regional

6.1.2.1 Policy dimension

Licensing procedures in Argentina vary from province to province. There isn't a method established at national level, but each region determines its own process. Particularly, In Tierra del Fuego, there is not a defined approach, moreover, it appears to be rather slow.

On the other hand, in Tierra del Fuego, one of the main challenges that aquaculture producers face is the customs policies since reaching national market involves an exportation procedure, hence, it represents a constraint to transport and commercialize the products elaborated in the region.

Although the transit policies were developed at the regional level, they undoubtedly have a major impact on the local context. For example, mussel consumed in Tierra del Fuego comes from Chile as importation fees are cheaper than producing locally. In this sense, interviewees have expressed that the government should reinforce or establish certain import restrictions to incentivize the development of local production in the region. It seems to be quite complicated for local producers from Tierra del Fuego to expand their products to other provinces of Argentina.

6.1.2.2 Environmental dimension

The province of Tierra del Fuego issued a bill prohibiting salmon farming in the region. In this regard, Argentina is the first country in the world to outlaw this activity.

It is relevant to emphasize that one of the main reasons this bill passed was because of the pressure of local stakeholders regarding the development of aquaculture activities in the region highlighting the importance and commitment of stakeholders advocating against salmon farming in Argentina.

In Tierra de Fuego there are several protected areas. In fact, the Mitre Peninsula was recently declared as Natural Protected Area, which resulted in a significant reduction of the available coastline for their

activities. In addition, another bill being discussed is the provincial law on the use of coast, which seems to be quite restrictive as to what activities are allowed in Tierra del Fuego. In interviewee's views aquaculture does not stand much of a chance in relation to this law.

6.1.2.3 Communication dimension

At the regional level, the communication among several agents involved in aquaculture is not quite fluid or strong since there is a lack of dialogue. It appears to be that actor's roles are blended. It is unclear what tasks each one should perform. Furthermore, it has been stated by the interviewees that the efforts to share information and data about aquaculture innovations should be strengthened. For instance, academic and scientific sectors should strengthen their communication channels before establishing a dialogue with policymakers and regulators. These data are fundamental for government agents to make informed and fair decisions within the industry.

In relation to the communication channels between government agencies and producers, in Tierra del Fuego, it is based on formal notes directed to the Secretariat of Livestock and Fisheries, which depends on the Ministry of Production of the province. Frequently, those notes are not responded by the authorities. Therefore, producers have to approach the institutions in person. Some other method reported is via email but this channel lacks formality.

Another approach described in the interviews is through the personal connection between producers and government agents, meaning that producers can reach them easier since the relationship is already established. On the other hand, associations play an important role when establishing communication channels with the administration, such as the fishing cluster that occasionally operated as channel for consultation, complaints, or demand. Even though, some producers may have a direct connection, it is more effective when associations or interest groups support the producer, especially when some claims are made at regional level.

6.1.3 Local

6.1.3.1 Social dimension

One of the main matters involving the local sphere is the Social License to Operate (SLO). This refers to the community's acceptance of an aquaculture activity being developed in the territory. There are several features at play within the SLO, for instance, the pressure of groups of interest, local regulations, environmental matters and perception or experience of previous practices. These may vary from one context to another.

In Argentina, especially in Tierra del Fuego, tourism is probably one of the most important concerns for the community when implementing aquaculture practices. Tourism represents one of the major economic incentives for the region. Hence, the implementation of any action that may have a negative repercussion in the natural resources, such as the landscape, influences the acceptance of aquaculture practices. Moreover, salmon farming has had quite a negative impact on people's perception regarding the development of aquaculture practices. Nowadays this continues to represent a major setback even when introducing innovations, as there is a lack of understanding of salmon production and other aquaculture systems.

Another factor that influences on the SLO is the feasibility of aquaculture practices to generate jobs for the local community. In this regard, the fact that this activity can promote the creation of new jobs for the community represents an opportunity to enhance its acceptance.

6.1.3.2 Communication dimension

It is important to highlight that when the scientific community reaches out to the producers, most of the time they respond. It appears to be that the experiences this community has had with the local producers is satisfactory. Nevertheless, efforts to collaborate among different agents at the local level should be reinforced, as well as knowledge transfer. On one hand, it has been addressed by the interviewees that producers must be willing to ask for assistance when needed, for instance, when the production is not succeeding, and thus, determine how academics and scientists can lend a hand so that together they can improve aquaculture innovations. Possible egos should be put aside, and the expertise of academics and scientists and the experience of producers should be considered. In other words, it will be ideal to reach a consensus between the knowledge of the two. It is important to listen from both sides, meaning if the scientific-academic system is to really respond to the needs of the territory, they must listen to what the territory needs, whether it comes from an artisanal producer or a fishing entrepreneur.

On the other hand, this issue needs to be addressed also at the administrative level, since it is essential that technicians working for the governmental institutions be present at the production sites, to visit them and get more familiar with them. To legislate, authorize and supervise procedures, it should be standard for these agents to be present at the production locations.

6.2 Brazil

6.2.1 National

6.2.1.1 Policy dimension

Licences or permits are quite lengthy to obtain since there is no established deadline for issuing a response. There are projects that have been cancelled due to this situation. Nowadays large productions are still facing obstacles to obtain a licence. Nevertheless, there are some circumstances in which these are not required, for example, if the aquaculture operation is on a small-scale and is being developed inland. Reduced number of technicians to analyse applications within the environmental agencies could be one of the main reasons affecting the proficiency of the process. In this regard, it is important to emphasize the role of the technicians. They must be extensively trained as it is their responsibility to authorize the undertaking of a project. In addition, their response should include a comprehensive feedback and assistance on how to improve the application so that it can be approved.

Aquaculture practice in Brazil have evolved in recent decades, but administrative procedures and department fragmentation within the government have remained the same. In addition, there is still no aquaculture agency that addresses specifically marine or environmental matters. For example, when using Union Waters (such as the sea or any other marine body) for aquaculture activities, several government agencies are involved. Hence, producers have to reach every one of them, which complicates the process.

Furthermore, it is necessary to update the Brazilian Law Nº 145, which has been in place since 1998. States update it but it only applies to their context and not the Basin. Often the Basin is an area made of several States. For instance, if there is a lake between two States, the permit is not issued by either State, but by the central government.

Another matter influencing the development of aquaculture is legislation's outdatedness. Aquaculture expansion is taking place in the country; however, the regulatory framework is not evolving at the same pace as the industry. It has been stated by interviewees that federal regulations are acceptable, but regional ones are more rigorous, and research needs to be conducted to understand in which cases it is possible to introduce certain species, such as algae. In fact, if the benefits of introducing said species are highlighted, more progress can be made.

Broadly, interviewees have highlighted that aquaculture production in Brazil aims at reaching the domestic market.

6.2.1.2 Environmental dimension

According to the views of the interviewees, sustainability matters are not contained within the country's legislative framework. Nevertheless, there are farms that are including sustainability indicators within their production due to market demand, mostly external. Farms and producers that export must meet higher requirements; even in the domestic market, they are starting to be adopted.

For example, Aquacerti's certification procedure incorporates an indicator that measures the emission of greenhouse gases. Therefore, the company can calculate how much a producer is emitting or sequestering. Moreover, they have expressed interest in using these as carbon credits. There is a voluntary market for this; however, there is still a lot to do in order to regulate it. The complete procedure to obtain carbon credits is still unknown.

Currently, producers are more interested in the economic benefits. However, there are certification companies that incorporate sustainability matters within their proposals for producers, and they are accepting it since it seems to help with the marketing campaign for their products.

The incorporation of sustainability indicators was encouraged by the Ministry of Fishing and Aquaculture. It was first introduced as a survey format and progressively the sustainability research network was created and later these indicators were developed. Thus, when talking about sustainably in the Brazilian context, environmental, economic, and social matters are considered main aspects to be addressed in regards to these indicators. In addition to this, it has been highlighted within the interviews by aquaculture stakeholders that the community must be also contemplated. Aquaculture practices need to adjust to these sustainability standards to grow, as these requirements are in increasing demand by diverse government entities and society. In this regard, Aquacerti's certification includes indicators that focus on sustainability assessment as is the Brazilian company's main objective to promote a sustainable production model.

There are several factors impacting the development of a potential IMTA system. For example, geographical distribution, cultural context, the selection of species (species with higher value or their availability to be consumed or marketed). In the south and northeast, the production is mainly based on Tilapia. However, in the Amazon region Tambaqui and *Arapaima gigas* (pirarucu) are primarily

grown. Therefore, for the products emerging through IMTA practices to be absorbed, the production chain must be previously established. It is pointless to grow a species that will not be consumed and hence it will not generate an economic revenue. In addition, environmental agencies have made valuable efforts with the introduction of algae, for example, for the formulation of plant-based fishing feed.

6.2.1.3 Social dimension

There is a large supermarket chain in Brazil that showed interest in the sustainability certification since they own a sustainable line of products, which fit perfectly with the indicators developed in Aquacerti's certification. The idea is acquiring products from only certified suppliers.

Presently, sustainability products fall into a niche market. Interviewees revealed the perspective in which society is willing to pay more for certified fish as its production has been developed in a sustainable manner and adding value to the local community. Nevertheless, it is relevant to understand other societal factors, such as the fact that not all individuals can afford, for example, to consume seafood or fish on a regular basis, let alone certified products.

6.2.1.4 Communication dimension

In Brazil, communication among several stakeholders involved in the development of aquaculture practices is not effective. The lack of communication is highlighted in this context. Nevertheless, the creation of a platform in which several actors can interact would be quite helpful to enhance the interaction and communication of stakeholders. For example, within the ASTRAL project, Aquaculture Helix was created. This platform operates a forum in which different agents involved in aquaculture express their demands about the needs of the sector. Another example is the Aquavita project, where stakeholders participate in meetings and more indicators are being created from the governance dimension. Furthermore, the importance of synergies among researchers, private sector, research projects, associations, academia, producers, and companies are highlighted by the interviewees.

Regarding IMTA, within the Brazilian context it is emphasized that stronger dissemination efforts are needed, as well as the involvement of more technical assistance personnel to discuss thoroughly this system and its benefits.

6.2.2 Regional

6.2.2.1 Policy dimension

In Brazil, monitoring mechanisms are rarely applied. Only in a few regions is there a control regarding the amount of water used for a fish farm or a control of how feed will reach a tank. For example, if a project is being developed, it means that an authorization was issued, however, there will be no problem if 5 tons of feed were used at first, and then the amount increased to 7 or 8 tons. No authorities or entities will conduct a monitoring procedure in relation to this.

Another factor influencing waiting times is the selection of species. Some of them are more challenging than others and, therefore, it is reflected within the procedure. Moreover, it also depends on the 12 hydrographic regions, which is contained in IBAMA's Law Nº 145 that establishes the guidelines for the introduction, reintroduction, and transfer of fish, crustaceans, molluscs, and aquatic macrophytes for aquaculture purposes, excluding ornamental animal species. Each region develops and follow their own regulations. Some are more rigid for some species than others.

For the environmental agency, not only is the description of the species necessary, but also the quality of the project. If it is not properly done, for example, if there is no treatment system, it will not be approved. In this regard, it is important to highlight the producers' educational background: if they are well prepared or trained, the project should be well designed and will have more chance to be approved.

Each state has a list of species that can be produced. Tilapia can be produced practically all over Brazil, but in some states its production is quite limited since it is considered an exotic species. So, this situation varies from state to state. Furthermore, research may be conducted if a project indicates that certain species hold an economic value of interest for production. Then a technical note can be made for IBAMA or, for example, the environmental agencies of the states.

6.3 Ireland

6.3.1 National

6.3.1.1 Policy dimension

It has been pointed out by interviewees that scientific data should be used within aquaculture legislation. These should be based on substantiated information to contribute to filling knowledge gaps. Building solid bridges between the scientific community and policymakers and regulators would definitely benefit the country's aquaculture industry. For instance, the development of the National

Strategic Plan represents an opportunity in which key information obtained through the outcomes from European, national, and international projects could be taken into consideration. Furthermore, introducing the concept of IMTA within this plan should be also seen as growth possibility for the aquaculture sector. Nonetheless, it is worth pointing out that while the “New Strategic Guidelines for More Sustainable and Competitive EU Aquaculture” are undoubtedly a positive contribution, they are conceived by the industry as a generic document that does not focus on legislation and/or cases specific to the sector.

Implementing formal consultation mechanisms into policies should be encouraged. This might be addressed in theory, but implementation is needed in the field. Consultation plans in relation to aquaculture species culture systems and development goals would be a way to engage with stakeholders. Inviting stakeholders to share their inputs and viewpoints would rise to a much higher level of involvement when engaging.

In Ireland, there is one innovative approach called “*scoping*” within the licencing procedure. In this regard, before applying for a licence, a discussion with the applicant takes place about the application purposes and the procedure. In general terms, licencing process is described by aquaculture stakeholders as slow and bureaucratic. They have indicated that occasionally when applying for a licence, some section of the query has to be handled by a different government entity and it requires time. Moreover, stakeholders perceived that if they were licencing conditions particularly for IMTA, the procedure would require more paperwork and bureaucracy. It is generally considered that the legislation represents a challenge for aquaculture growth as it is rigid, laborious, and slow. It involves the coordination of several entities, and it is a three-layered process, with no guarantees of success.

The lack of flexibility is also underlined in relation to licencing procedures. Stakeholders have reported that the system is single species oriented and is not designed to facilitate the adoption of new technologies. Thus, the system is not yet fully prepared to accommodate IMTA. Moreover, the importance of the role of the technician in charge of dealing with the licence has also been mentioned. In fact, the key tool employed by regulators to make decisions regarding granting licences is the Environmental Impact Assessment. So, this mechanism is quite relevant for this context.

Another matter worth highlighting is the application of the legislation. In Ireland, the legislation is robust enough and in place, but its implementation is an aspect that merits focus. For instance, several entities are embedded in either marine or even environmental policy, as well as multiple pieces of

legislation across multidisciplinary departments. This situation makes it quite complex to reach the objective of complying with it. Therefore, aquaculture stakeholders are demanding a more efficient and transparent licencing system.

In terms of adopting participatory approaches, the industry is quite small and knows all its politicians, therefore, they don't experience any problems regarding the feasibility of getting their views across. Although, stakeholders perceive that there are no sectors within the industry with more leverage on policy, there are circumstances in which groups such as NGO have better opportunity to influence policy. For example, there's a piece of legislation currently going through government and there was pre-legislative scrutiny, as part of that. One of the committees, is responsible for holding several hearings, scrutinising the heads of Bill of that legislation, and extend invitations to various stakeholders. However, the seafood sector (fisheries and aquaculture agents) was not invited, while the NGOs and offshore wind did get the opportunity to participate. Therefore, they would have more leverage on policy regarding protected areas than the seafood sector.

6.3.1.2 Environmental dimension

Monitoring programmes are part of the country's requirements for issuing licences. Water column and benthic on the seabed are one of the types of monitoring being carried out by industry. In this regard, relevant data obtained through them must be public, transparent, and shared among the various stakeholders to improve aquaculture practices. This information could be used to make decisions on the renewal, extension, or the rejection of licences. Likewise, these systems are quite helpful for industry to comprehend what is needed to prove that the product is safe for consumption.

Furthermore, concerns are raised about how the Water Framework Directive in relation to other activities on shore are managed. For instance, effluent outfalls from villages and towns; its regulation and proper application in these areas is a matter of particular interest, especially to the shellfish industry as it's impacting on the quality of the bays and the water bodies that shellfish has been operating in. Another example is Water Framework Directive surveillance and operational monitoring. In this case, if the issue is related to the broader environmental indicators, an investigative monitoring tool is undertaken to find the potential cause, however, implementing it takes time.

On the other hand, Marine Protected Areas (MPA) are likely to affect many existing frameworks and directives, such as the Water Framework Directive and Natura 2000 sites. MPA legislation is likely to be the main legislative instrument in terms of water quality and the environment. Nonetheless, it is

still not clearly defined what an MPA entails. Some sector members perceived that no activity can be carried out in that area, others would point out that some can be developed, such as low impacting activities, and others would indicate that those activities that directly impact the feature for which this area was designated might not be allowed. Having a clear definition of MPAs and their impacts in terms of aquaculture practices would be helpful. Furthermore, industry members have indicated a connection among marine protected areas, nature, the environment, and aquaculture, but it needs to be handled correctly. Interviewees have mentioned that co-creation strategies must be established to foster an open dialogue to define the measures to be implemented in this regard.

Collaboration is required between industry and legislation to highlight or incentivize the environmental benefits of aquaculture, especially of IMTA systems as the latter incorporates circularity matters. Emphasizing this feature could lead to its incorporation by regulators within the Environmental Impact Assessment.

Lastly, the possible effects of climate change on the aquaculture industry must be considered. Producers have experienced impacts such as warming seas, meteorological phenomenon such as storms and more emerging threats. For instance, there are around 20-30 sites where the Pacific oyster is now reproducing, whereas twenty years ago there were only 2 in the whole country. Industry needs to be adaptable to face the upcoming environmental challenges through the adoption of other species or perhaps relocate their facilities to sites where temperatures are more stable.

6.3.1.3 Social dimension

Most frequently, society is not aware of aquaculture practices, let alone of what IMTA consists of. Lack of accurate information influences the social acceptance towards this type of production. Educational strategies and plans need to be put into place to increase awareness among society. Stakeholders declared that perhaps, some sort of demonstration approach or tangible results would play a major role in achieving this.

Research funded by different entities, such as the European Union have enhanced the promotion of aquaculture and its sustainable strategies. Nevertheless, the discussion around blue economy, carbon sequestration and minimizing effects and impacts of this activity, remains merely a conversation.

On the other hand, it is pointed out by interviewees that producers are willing to use certification schemes. A while ago the Irish aquaculture industry decided to convert to organic to compete against

large producing nations like Scotland and Norway. More so, the use of certifications as GLOBALG.A.P. is closely related to consumer desire. The market demands it, and the industry delivers it.

Although, there is no specific certifications for IMTA, the same principles can be applied within the standards ones. It can be covered through sustainable management of the water body and how the resources are managed while developing the activity. Differentiation concerning sustainable features or categories should be highlighted.

The two main sectors within Irish aquaculture that are 100% certified are: organic salmon and mussels. Some products are certified for different purposes, for example for consumers reassurance and as a marketing tool. The first one is more related to food safety concerns especially when involving certain species (that does not pose a risk to consumers). The latter refers more to the implementation of labels to underline certain aspects of the product, e.g., organic labelling.

In Ireland society's understanding of aquaculture practices is quite limited, especially regarding IMTA and its benefits. In other words, there is not enough knowledge for lack of acceptance. Objections are addressed under environmental concerns, but it seems to be that the main issue is the potential visual impact as IMTA practices require large spaces to be developed.

6.3.1.4 Communication dimension

Monitoring is considered by stakeholders as an essential mechanism. It has been stated by interviewees that it shouldn't be based on conducting the activity itself, but to put effort into communicating and identifying the impact of aquaculture production and how it should be addressed.

Although policies might not be developing at the same pace as industry is, there is determination to introduce research and scientific components into legislation to support industry agents. The mutual support of all these actors plays a significant role and is intertwined. Joint efforts are called for to build synergies that will really generate a positive impact on aquaculture. Furthermore, this should also contemplate IMTA systems.

In Ireland, one method of strengthening synergies and knowledge exchange is through the consolidation of working groups, which collaborate in technical working seminars to exchange best practices. Broadly, participation of policy makers from the different Member States is essential since

scientific data is shared, and these must be aware of the new techniques or innovations so that they can legislate properly.

6.3.2 Local

In Ireland, there was a moment in which the foreshore and the aquaculture licence were combined in one department for aquaculture. It was quite efficient yet complicated.

There are several groups that seek the active involvement of local aquaculture community that operate as a collective entity representing the voice of the sector. For example, there are the fisheries organisations and CLAMS system (Coordinated Local Aquaculture Management System). The latter is government funded.

6.4 Scotland

6.4.1 National

6.4.1.1 Policy dimension

The precautionary principle might be limiting the advancement of IMTA practices, is an important trait highlighted throughout the interviews. This principle is underpinned by the SEPA regulation for aquaculture, and it's distinguished by its tendency to hinder innovation. In other words, the default position of this principle is to prohibit any activity when situations of uncertainty arise as future implications are unknown. Certainly, innovative approaches and technologies are easier to develop under a more flexible legislation and more adaptive management. Undoubtedly, science and innovation constitute major contributors to policy. Nonetheless, it is widely acknowledged that innovations evolve faster than legislation.

There are a variety of issues influencing licensing procedures. First of all, several agencies intervene, e.g., local government issues planning consent and occasionally consent for a Crown Estate lease is required from the Crown Estate Scotland, and sometimes a marine licence is also needed from Marine Scotland and the Scottish Government. It also involves the application of two different licensing processes: planning and marine. This constitutes a duplication of efforts and resources, especially for the finfish industry as there is some sort of overlap between what is considered under EIA, which relates with planning permission, and the aspects that are consented and regulated through CAR licence process. Secondly, it appears to be that organisations are understaffed and in some cases expertise to handle applications is lacking. Thirdly, costly and extensive waiting times are experienced without guaranteeing a positive response. Similarly, there is no checklist or a simple method to verify

that all the criteria are met. Additionally, the complexity of the process is affecting negatively small companies and producers as they don't have considerable experience dealing with these approaches. However, this situation does not seem to affect large companies. In addition, it is crucial to underline that some licences are handled by different authorities and legislative frameworks depending on specific species. For instance, shellfish farms are managed under the Town and Country Planning Act. Nonetheless, if seaweed introduction is planned, a separate licence under the Marine licence is required as cultivating seaweed under the Town and Country Planning Act is prohibited. Another challenging case would be an IMTA proposal incorporating finfish, shellfish, and seaweed cultivation. Three separate approaches would be required for its development. Some guidance on how to deal with applications for multiple species at a single site, or within a bay/area (Integrated Coastal Area Management, or ICAM strategy) would be highly beneficial for the industry.

Furthermore, incentive schemes by government can be used to promote the development of IMTA systems through subsidies and support regarding nutrient reduction and biodiversity, and nutrient, and carbon credits. These are not currently being implemented. However, there is funding available from the Marine Fund Scotland for seaweed developments, hence, industry can apply if they propose a project that would benefit seaweed or shellfish farms.

Moreover, there is a strong policy drive as efforts to conduct a large revision of the aquaculture policy regulation were completed. The updated Scottish Aquaculture Framework is still yet to be introduced. In fact, one of the key challenges the country is currently facing is the restructuration of regulatory frameworks and legislation to properly accommodate the implementation of IMTA systems.

Participatory approaches are also a relevant subject within the Scottish context. Online and face-to-face consultation is well promoted. In addition, there are various avenues and channels available in which industry can reach policymakers. However, some sectors, such as finfish aquaculture might have more leverage on influencing political decisions as they have a more extensive basis and platform to be heard.

Lastly, Brexit is a subject that influences the aquaculture sector. Regarding policy matters, it seems to be relatively similar than before since Europe is still a big importer/exporter. Moreover, it will impact funding regimes such as Horizon as the government has replaced these funding schemes to an extent, but in no way to the same magnitude. Shellfish production will be also affected due to its proximity to the European market as seafood trade involves time-consuming bureaucratic procedures. In this

regard, any sort of delay could cause products such as shellfish to spoil. These impacts will be reflected in the future, as further divergences between UK and European regulation emerge. In general terms it appears to be that Scottish Government is willing to keep regulations well aligned with the European legislation.

6.4.1.2 Environmental dimension

Current legislation concerning environmental protection is described by interviewees as ambiguous since continuous review and accountability measures are not contained within. Agencies' roles are mostly focused on compliance enforcement with the thresholds and limitations of granted authorizations. In practice, this rarely works, especially regarding marine environment as it is extremely difficult access. In this regard, self-monitoring or other kind of reporting function is implemented.

Environmental monitoring is necessary to identify if a farm is complying with the environmental standards established as part of the licencing procedure. But beyond that, it represents an opportunity to understand the health of the features of the protected area and to determine whether further management is required to address potential risk concerning the feature's health. The seabed monitoring is the only one that is implemented routinely, and it is performed by the farm operators. So, they take seabed samples at the end of each production cycle and send them to a server. This sector run their own analysis and lastly SEPA determines if the seabed standards are met for the CAR licence for that specific farm.

From an environmental perspective, within aquaculture activity exists various opportunities for using waste products to create high/low and different value products. Currently in the country there are several companies that innovate in procedures that seek to utilise waste from aquaculture practices and examine how it can be integrated into the aquatic supply chain. However, when referring to multi-trophic aquaculture, some complications to consider arise. For instance, to accurately absorb all waste, the amount of algae that needs to be grown would cover an area that represents hectares, which would bring consequences for navigation, fishing and even access by the boats.

It is fundamental to address the relationship between climate change and aquaculture. Some effects originated by this situation are affecting the development of said practices, for instance, the fish cannot migrate to escape the rising temperatures as their wild counterparts could. Moreover, regarding acid acidification, just a tiny alteration might affect the function, composition, and generate

stress carrying new diseases. Some species might be further affected by these effects. In this regard, the Scottish industry has indicated that finfish aquaculture is definitely under pressure.

The International Union for Conservation (IUCN) has multiple categories for the designation of protected areas. The highest level of protection indicates that only scientific activity can be developed within those MPAs. Currently, aquaculture practices can be implemented within some MPAs. On the other hand, Highly Protected Marine Areas (HMPAs) will soon be introduced in Scotland and will prohibit all forms of aquaculture in the 10% of those HMPAs. It is, therefore, key to address the purpose of a specific MPA. For instance, if the MPA is zoned because of the wading bird population, then a seaweed farm 200 meters away would have no impact on the protected feature. Therefore, there should be no reason why a seaweed farm in a MPA that is designed to protect wading birds couldn't be established. Any potential effects between the development and the protected feature could be mitigated to avoid any significant impacts.

6.4.1.3 Social dimension

Aquaculture activity does play an important role in terms of economic contribution to a series of rural and fragile areas in the West Coast of Scotland. The main issue is trying to find balance while accepting the potential effect that these practices might have but ensuring that developments are located appropriately so that significant impacts on key habitats and species of conservation importance can be avoided.

Therefore, engaging with local communities and proving that their necessities have been considered should be a condition for the granting of a licence. It, nevertheless, can be challenging as the local population might be resistant to accepting the development of these systems, as they are unfamiliar with their procedure and their possible implications. The introduction of educational strategies highlighting what aquaculture is about and its positive outcomes within the community, would possibly increase awareness among the population.

It is important to point out that populations are now more aware and interested in environmental protection. Attitudes have shifted over the last 15 – 20 years and now society is far more vigilant. It has been stated by interviewees within this context that, there is a link between regulations and social licence. There is a tendency for society to view it as the government's duty to regulate the industry, and if it follows the established regulations, then the activity is being developed accordingly. When the lack of trust in government's capacity to fulfil their responsibilities, such as protecting the environment

arises, then the social licence aspect becomes more complex. Another subject highlighted was the modern and broader concept of community. The acceptance and perception of society is not only focused on the coastal communities in which production is being developed, but also involves views of communities built up through communication outlets and social media. For instance, interviewees revealed that information published in newspapers has an eminent impact.

6.4.1.4 Communication dimension

In Scotland, approaches already in place for fostering cooperation between the policy sphere and scientists have been identified by stakeholders involved in the aquaculture sector, for instance, the willingness of Marine Scotland Science to provide assistance when necessary. Interviewees have declared that strategies that seek deeper collaboration between actors ought to be pursued. Embedding policymakers and regulators within the innovation sphere for activate co-development activities would be beneficial for the improvement of the aquaculture industry. Thus, government actors would be acquainted with innovations and implementations of technologies within the field, which would be very fruitful when making future decisions.

It was also addressed within the interviews that industry needs to be considered as well. All three (industry, academia/science and legislation) should jointly cooperate in bridging this gap. On one hand, stakeholders mentioned that it would be convenient for industry to regulate the pace of its expansion, so that research efforts can be scaled up to industry levels. Additionally, they underlined that better articulation and active communication are required among these sectors. For instance, novel research avenues could be proposed by industry, and could provide initial data regarding how the incorporation of mechanisms and technologies is progressing. On the other hand, it is necessary to reiterate that this collaboration is not unilateral, and that the administration must also strive to increase the levels of engagement with the other sectors. For example, industry participation is not currently being intensively promoted, which generates the feeling among the sector that they are relatively unheard and frustrated with government. There have been some significant efforts from the Scottish government to engage with industry. In this regard, meetings with a working group including lawyers and the trade body of the Association of Scottish Shellfish Growers were taking place until cancellation due to COVID. So, this sector would go to Victoria Quay¹ and interact with policymakers and regulators. Thus, information and experiences regarding what was occurring in the field were shared with

¹ The building became part of the Scottish Government (until 2007 known as the Scottish Executive) following the devolution of powers to the Scottish Parliament in 1999. It is now the largest single office of the Government, home to several departments and functions, including policy, development, education, environment, transport and planning.

government. A similar experience was registered with the Scottish Seaweed Industry Association. A close relationship was built between them through a funded development officer post for the trade body. The purpose of this channel was to create contact with the seaweed producers. Furthermore, these two sectors hold conferences annually and the intervention of the government is always encouraged.

6.5 South Africa

6.5.1 National

6.5.1.1 Policy dimension

Overall, the current legislation is clear enough for the aquaculture sector, but it is worth noting that freshwater and seawater operations have two different legislative frameworks, which may cause confusion among industry members. In this regard, the introduction of the proposed Aquaculture Development Bill is expected to improve matters.

Regarding administration interaction, national government is responsible for marine aquaculture and most of its authorisation and permits. On the other hand, environmental approvals depend on provincial management, and lastly, there may be zoning regulations or property matters that fall under the jurisdiction of the municipality. So, different government departments are involved and needed for aquaculture development in South Africa.

During recent years there has been real growth within the governance of the industry. Elements such as labour aspects, waste management, environmental matters, permitting procedures, reporting duties and animal health concerns have been considered. In addition, engagement with entities seems to be adequate since they are willing to assist and provide reasonable responses and arguments. On the other hand, the inspection exercise is firmer. If there is something that might not be functioning according to the established requirements, all activities will cease until that situation is sorted. Also, there are quite numerous permits involved. For instance, a permit to harvest kelp is needed as well as another for an employed tractor to transport it. In addition, it must be roadworthy, even if it's driven on the beach, and if you change vehicle or boat, activities will cease until the permit is amended. These procedures and modifications are costly and time consuming.

In the South African context, the market is not at a stage where the implication of using certification schemes is widely known. Some producers have attempted to implement certification systems, but it rather seems to be a costly and complicated process since there are some limitations that hinder the

procedure, such as laboratory support. In this regard, the inspectors found that the laboratories employed by abalone farms exporting to the EU market did not adhere to the certification requirements. Moreover, industry is still developing in this country, therefore, auditors have to be flown in from other countries, which represent an added expense.

In general terms, certifications have sometimes been perceived as profit-making operations. Several companies from different sectors have disassociated from certification schemes, for example Woolworths. In this sense, the following questions arise: Have the dynamics changed? Do consumers trust the company more instead of the certification systems? Is it possible to have a substantial market impact without the implementation of these?

Under this premise, discussions about the feasibility of implementing self-management and self-certification procedures have been addressed by the industry. On the other hand, the Department of Forestry, Fisheries, and the Environment (DFFE) have developed a certification framework for aquaculture integrating four pillars: environmental, social, food safety and aquatic animal health and welfare. They carried out a comparative legislative framework to identify how they meet international requirements. Furthermore, they have helped industry navigate certification procedures, but there is a wide variety of schemes, and generally they are linked to a certain market. For example, if producers are attempting to access the Asian market, they probably try to adhere to GLOBALG.A.P. or ASC certifications. There is no certification system that fits all the requirements.

Regarding the licencing procedure, it does not represent a setback, but it is definitely tedious since it is a lengthy and bureaucratic procedure. Also, it involves a certain level of complexity and is, therefore, challenging to navigate, specifically if a producer is applying on its own. Currently, the process seems to have improved as waiting periods have been reduced.

Furthermore, there are several regulations involved in aquaculture development such as the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), National Environmental Management Act (NEMA), Marine Living Resource Act (MLRA) when introducing alien species. This also may cause potential bureaucratic issues since industry might need various authorisations in place before starting an operation, but it will depend on every case. Operation Phakisa is an effective approach that has helped to engage and streamline the process. This cross-sector programme fosters the participation of various stakeholders that engage to design concrete actions to address potential barriers regarding development issues highlighted in the National Development Plan (NDP) 2030.

Formal incentives for the application of IMTA practices are lacking. Nevertheless, government is willing to design and implement concrete actions to encourage its development, especially within the abalone operations since it appears to be more suited for IMTA. Moreover, the possibility for seaweed farming to be tied in with mussel or oyster farming has been envisaged.

Lastly, certain situations in South Africa need to be discussed. The industry has reported that some of their products are sold through illegal channels. In other words, stocks confiscated by the government are sold via auctions. This represents a major risk as food safety is not guaranteed.

6.5.1.2 Environmental dimension

Environmental dimension is a highly important matter when developing aquaculture practices. In South Africa, there have been situations in which companies have faced difficulties. These are registered at the Department of Affairs and usually companies are required to submit a formal rectification plan to address the situation. In one specific case, the result was a civil project whereby all outlet water from the farm will be screened to eliminate any foreign materials leaving the farm. This action will positively impact on the company's BAP certification process. Another incident was also reported, in which bags used for feed reached the environment. Thus, a plan was designed to manage the situation. Every Friday a cleaning expedition was sent from the farm's outlet along the coast, and the results are recorded and monitored.

There is no legislation that addresses the application of IMTA practices in South Africa. However, it could be supported through permits to grow multiple species, concrete actions such as rewards systems or the incorporation of novel technologies. Knowledge gaps currently exist around IMTA, such as the disease risk, food safety, and technology around certain species. A regulatory framework to allow industry to develop to an extent on an experimental basis would lead to better comprehension of the impact of these practices on all levels. It is worth mentioning that research around IMTA procedures is being conducted, but inputs are not actively being promoted.

In addition, industry have highlighted the potential benefits of implementing IMTA procedures, especially within abalone farms as they grow seaweed in their effluent and then use it to feed the abalone. Multiple benefits have emerged from this practice, such as clean effluent water, but the real advantage is for the farm itself since the abalone do well on a diet based on fresh algae. Yet, developing

these practices must be economically viable, for instance, contemplating the possibility of trading credits, although carbon sequestration and credits procedures need to be explored within the country.

Currently, there are no certification schemes specifically for IMTA systems. However, it can be promoted or accommodated through existing ones, such as GLOBALG.A.P. as it groups species. Another example are the environmental benefits of developing IMTA practices, and therefore, it can be adhered to the MSC certification.

In South Africa, the environmental monitoring is currently funded by DFFE. This situation will be adjusted shortly, and the industry will be responsible for performing it as well as dealing with the expenses of it. Also, a thorough environmental legislation is in place under the National Environmental Management Act and Marine Living Resources Act (MLRA). Environmental legislation is adequate and well-rehearsed. In fact, if companies do not comply with environmental monitoring programmes permits will not be renewed.

In addition, some of the measurements integrated within the legislation is the restriction of aquaculture discharge into a protected area. Furthermore, stakeholders consider that MPA's must not be combined with aquaculture practices as they constitute primary element of natural resource conservation.

Lastly, it is essential to highlight that climate change will have an impact on aquaculture practices, e.g., temperature alterations could result in stress in the species and make them vulnerable to diseases.

6.5.1.3 Social dimension

Aquaculture social perception can be enhanced by promoting the benefits of implementing certain practices, such as with IMTA highlighting its circularity features and its positive impact on the environment.

The social licence system requires an active, well-educated market. In South Africa, certain non-scientific concerns arose within society. Issues regarding sharks and faeces washing up on the beach were addressed. Society does not know the whole process of aquaculture operations, and sometimes negative assumptions can be made. Hence, educational efforts must be enhanced to emphasize how aquaculture can be environmentally sustainable and IMTA sets the course on this matter.

In terms of marketability, the more environmentally friendly, the better the market perception is. Using certification schemes might increase the feasibility of aquaculture products being accepted. Furthermore, the issue of food safety is more oriented towards the European market, as consumers are more concerned about the origin of products and how they are grown. This does not seem to apply in the South African context as seafood is not widely consumed. Nonetheless, this is still a very important matter for the country's aquaculture production, and it's addressed in the legislation as its products are aimed at reaching international markets.

Lastly, this topic represents both risk and opportunities. On the positive side, IMTA is associated with green marketing opportunities. On the downside some concerns arose related to society's resistance to eating products that feed on waste. However, it was suggested that these perceptions were predominantly a short-term risk, as there is a tendency for public attitudes to change.

6.5.1.4 Communication dimension

In South Africa, there are several communication endeavours. One example is the Aquaculture Association of Southern Africa (AASA) conference with positive examples of establishing and strengthening synergies between the research and industry fields. It counts with the extensive participation of the industry sector and focuses on presenting different and new technology as well as its benefits.

It is necessary to clarify that some aquaculture sectors have more leverage regarding the establishment of communication channels. The Abalone Farmers Association of South Africa has regular interactions with government institutions since it dominates the aquaculture space in the country. But this situation doesn't seem to significantly affect other producers as if one sector gets relief from regulations, it generally benefits the other ones. Furthermore, communication through associations appears to be the only approach to engage with the policies at government level.

It is crucial to highlight that smaller producers do not possess the same resources as other sectors. Thus, establishing adequate communication channels with government is challenging. This can lead to producers feeling that their opinions are not considered or heard. On the contrary, the abalone industry benefits from a greater leverage as more producers attend meetings to provide input. It is also a considerable job creator and revenue generator compared to other industries. Trout aquaculture is a smaller subsector that includes retired lawyers that are now fly fishing with the

capacity to leverage policy. Hence, the feasibility to engage with government is money-driven and it depends on the size of the industry.

Regarding the process for setting up a farm, individuals can contact the Department of Forestry, Fisheries, and the Environment (DFFE) via email to request information. Moreover, platforms have been set up so that industry can address issues under AquaSA or subsectors that represent AquaSA. Furthermore, to formally engage with industry a liaison meeting takes place quarterly. However, the DFFE does not communicate regularly with freshwater aquaculture as its regulation doesn't fall under their jurisdiction.

Also, the DFFE has created an aquaculture liaison committee that gathers once every month or two. It is a multi-role player group that functions as an effective platform to engage government agents and academics involving all the subsectors in the industry.

Lastly, it has been addressed by interviewees that funding research that focuses on the benefits of marketability for IMTA products needs to be supported. Having proven cases of IMTA can improve and encourage its development. Without hesitation research and collaborative projects facilitate better understanding in government about what is involved and needed for production. For example, when introducing new species, a research team is actively involved within the DFFE to facilitate the introduction of scientific breakthroughs in policies.

6.5.2 Regional

Regional and national import and export permits are needed to move species in South Africa. However, this is more applicable to freshwater aquaculture, and it falls under provincial mandate, whereas marine concerns national entities. In this sense, diverse requirements are established for each procedure, which require interaction with different government levels. It has also been stated by interviewees that a quite clear system is in place which indicates what steps are needed to be taken to follow the process.

6.5.3 Local

In South Africa, the social reality is different among aquaculture and IMTA possibilities. For instance, Wild Coast Abalone (WCA) is in one of the poorest regions of South Africa with unemployment of 50%. The common perception expressed by interviewees is that just providing jobs is all the Social Licence

required at the local level. However, there are isolated cases where abalone farms have not been developed due to lack of community support. This seems to be more economic driven.

At the local level, there are many actions that could be implemented to enhance trust in aquaculture practices, such as the introduction of workshops, educative dynamics at schools, building bridges between society and aquaculture producers. Community is not quite aware of what aquaculture entails, let alone IMTA systems. This represents an opportunity for producers, researchers, scientists to strengthen this bridge. Actions with concrete objectives must be implemented, such as invitations to society to visit aquaculture production centres.

The potential environmental impact is clearly a factor influencing the SLO. This matter is something that society takes into consideration and could increase the social acceptability within a certain territory. The promotion of more sustainable aquaculture systems with lower environmental impact could represent a turning point for SLO. It is essential that society internalize that aquaculture does not mean salmon farming and that nowadays there are quite a few innovations, such as IMTA, that allow the recirculation of nutrients and therefore does not represent a threat to the environment.

In addition, the relationship between regulations and social licence is built within the EIA, which is a process that aims at contributing to the social economic development. In South Africa, community participation is a requirement within the EIA. Therefore, if the operation is taking place in a community land, there must be actions fostering participation. Occasionally, projects do not get off the ground because they lack community support.

7 Recommendations

- No current regulations for IMTA systems, however, it can be addressed within aquaculture legislation through environmental, sustainable, and technical innovation aspects.
- If there are regulations on fish and a number of invertebrates, regulations on seaweeds are absent in many countries and should be developed.
- Updated and flexible legislation and regulatory framework are required to address IMTA.
- Review and update legislation to avoid potential contradictions at national, regional, and local levels.
- Aspects such as the change of government periodically should be considered as a relevant factor for the optimal development of IMTA.

- Increase understanding of IMTA systems and enhance the expertise of policy makers and regulators.
 - Improve the capacity and build the expertise of government staff.
 - More technical assistance for licencing procedures.
 - Investments regarding aquaculture agreed during previous legislation must be guaranteed.
 - Further cooperation among producers, researchers, scientists, and regulators is key to promote more novel technologies within the aquaculture industry.
 - Well-informed decisions based on science by policymakers and regulators are essential.
 - The incorporation of participatory approaches in decision-making processes involving a wide variety of stakeholders, must be reinforced.
 - Introduce One-stop-shop approach to address administrative fragmentation.
 - Feasibility to implement IMTA systems at an experimental and small-scale level should be relatively easy.
 - Develop regulations for species to enhance the development of IMTA systems.
 - Increase awareness of the environmental benefits of IMTA practices.
 - Future pathways need to be developed to enable carbon and other nutrient credits processes.
 - The feasibility to accommodate multiple species in one licence should be pursued.
 - Promote the proper use of concepts in relation to IMTA practices. For example, avoid the use of terms such as "fish wastes/faeces". "Co-products or by-products" can be used instead.
- Increasing the societal acceptability of IMTA will require the use of appropriate vocabulary to develop the appropriate image.

8 Further considerations

Undoubtedly, the reinforcement of the legislation is one of the main research lines that should be addressed in the near future in order to facilitate the insertion of new technologies in the aquaculture sector. In addition, the cultural context plays a major role in social acceptance. For example, in Tierra del Fuego most of the production generated through aquaculture systems is developed either for exportation or for the consumption by tourists visiting the region. This is due to the cultural context; Argentina is well-known for its meat consumption. In this regard, more research needs to be done focusing on the cultural aspects surrounding aquaculture production which should steer actions and recommendations for new policies which enable or promote the real potential of IMTA.

Another suitable example takes place in South Africa, where seaweeds and abalone are produced and then exported to Asia. In the western world, these products are not as popular. This raises the question

whether farms should be established in Europe in order to export to Asia? Or should the market in Europe be improved? And if so, what could be the best approach to do so? Would the information and promotion of novel products be enough to enhance their acceptance in the Atlantic countries?

Perhaps, the development of more creative dissemination methods could increase awareness within society. For instance, in France, *France Haliotis* is currently creating specific recipes for algae. Possibly offering tastings of these novel products to the public can contribute to promoting their market acceptance. This company is implementing IMTA systems growing abalone and seaweeds. It is a family company that has developed a good relationship with the local community. Thus, the aquaculture practices are embraced. In addition, they have developed strategies to increase awareness within the community; for instance, they welcome people, especially children from schools, to explain the procedures and implications of the activity. Moreover, invitations are extended during the weekends to families to attend the facility and see how they grow seaweeds and abalone together.

A company called *Algafres*, in Spain, is starting the new and first IMTA facility in Galicia. They are working with seaweeds and sea urchins: the sea urchins feed on seaweeds and they are moved to the ocean bottom to try to restore the population. The capture of sea urchin is also a traditional activity in Galicia. In that way, they are combining tradition and the development of new aquaculture techniques, such as IMTA. The population, the fisheries and the local areas are welcoming this new activity.

Furthermore, it is important to consider and to keep in mind other situations where IMTA is being developed. There is no doubt that Asian countries have successfully developed IMTA practices for a long time. Currently, China produces roughly 60% of world mariculture, with 40% done through IMTA systems. Hence, China's IMTA production represents 24% of world's mariculture. We should wonder how much of the Chinese IMTA model is adaptable to Atlantic IMTA scenarios, considering that societal context and labour conditions, prices, salaries, etc are much different.

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